

STUDY AND DIRECTION OF DEVELOPMENT OF SEMANTIC PROPERTIES OF WORDS AND PHRASES

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Resume: The article is devoted to combinatorial semasiology, which is a description of the relationship between the semantics of a word and its compatibility. A word, in order to be combined with another word, has a certain meaning, in which its compatibility is already embedded, which is an important proper linguistic indicator of this meaning.

Keywords: semantics, lexical meaning, syntagmatics, compatibility, syntagmatic aspect of the meaning of a word, restrictions on compatibility, combinatorial properties of words.

One of the main provisions of modern linguistics concerns the interpretation of language as a semantic system in its functioning. At various levels of language, such a concept as a semantic field is put forward as a complex unit of analysis. The historical extent of the study of field theory and its current state allows a deeper insight into the essence of the field, its structure and application.

Interest in the study of the systemic organization of the vocabulary of a language, semantic changes in the meanings of words, is manifested in the existence of lexico-semantic associations of words in the form of various groups, rows, fields. After all, a systematic approach to the study of more and more new fragments of the dictionary allows you to identify the individual characteristics of lexical units in the process of combining them, to better comprehend the systemic patterns of the language.

The term "lexicology" consists of two Greek words: lexis - "word, phrase" (respectively, lexicos - "related to the word") and logos - "teaching, science". Thus, lexicology as a term literally means "the science of the word". However, the name gives only a general idea of the goals and subject of this area of linguistic science, because all other sections of the latter also consider the word, but from a different point of view. (For example, phonetics studies the phonetic structure of a language, i.e., the system of

phonemes and intonation, considers the external sound form of a word. Grammar, which is inextricably linked with lexicology, studies the grammatical structure of a language. It considers various means of expressing grammatical relationships between words and those models by which words are combined into phrases and sentences).

Interestingly, many linguists have tried to define the word as a linguistic phenomenon. But none of the definitions is comprehensive and accurately reflects all aspects of this unique product of human communication. Also, it is not yet fully understood what a language is, the fundamental unit of which is the word.

Nevertheless, it can be said that there are no accidents in the vocabulary of a language, that each word represents the smallest unit in a vast, efficient and perfectly balanced system of language. Under the vocabulary (or stock) of the language (vocabulary of a language or language stock) we will mean the entire set of words in it.

So what do we know about the word?

First, the word is a unit of speech and serves the purposes of human communication. Thus, the word can be characterized as a unit of communication.

Secondly, a word can be considered as a set of its constituent sounds, transmitted in writing by a sequence of graphic symbols.

Thirdly, if the word is analyzed from a structural point of view, then it has a number of characteristics. Linguists traditionally distinguish the external and internal structure of the word.

The external structure of a word is its morphological structure. For example, in the phrase a breathtakingly beautiful view, the word breathtakingly can be broken down into the following morphemes: the two root stems breath -, - take -, the participle suffix - ing and the adverb suffix - ly. All these morphemes make up the external structure of the word breathtakingly.

The external structure of the word and typical word-formation patterns are studied in the section of lexicology called "C word formation".

The internal structure of a word, or its meaning, is usually called the semantic structure of the word. This is one of the main aspects of the word. Words can serve as a

means of communication only due to their meaning, each of the words of the language has a semantic function, naming various denotations (objects, phenomena, properties, actions). This aspect of the word is as important as its external organization. The question of the initial motivation between the meaning of a word and its sound form is complicated. Apparently, such a motivation existed, but was lost over time, except for those words that are formed according to the principle of onomatopoeia (imitate the sounds of the denotations they denote), for example: clatter, rattle, croak. Secondary motivation can be identified in names and surnames (for example: English - Victor , translated from Latin means "winner"; English - Nataly , translated from Greek means "native", etc.). It is very interesting to trace the processes of changing the meaning of words and creating new formations with the advent of new denotations or the appearance of new properties in familiar objects. The branch of lexicology that studies the meaning of a word is called semantics.

Another structural property (aspect) of a word is its unity. The word has both external (formal) and internal (semantic) unity. The formal unity of a word is sometimes erroneously understood as its indivisibility. However, how then to consider the word breathtakingly? After all, from a structural point of view, this word can be divided into components. In this case, it is interesting to compare a compound word and a phrase consisting of the same components. The difference between the word blackbird (blackbird) and the phrase a black bird (black bird) is best illustrated by the example of their place in the grammatical system of the language. The first (blackbird) has a unity of form (written together), has a single grammatical design (in the plural - blackbirds). The first word component (black -) is not subject to grammatical changes. As for the phrase a black bird, then each of its components can acquire independent grammatical forms: the blackest birds I've ever seen . In addition, other words can be placed between the components of the specified phrase (black night bird), which is not possible in the case of the word blackbird.

The same example can be used to show what is meant by semantic unity. In the phrase black bird each of the significant words corresponds to a separate concept: bird -

a living being; black - color. In contrast, the word blackbird conveys only one concept - the type of bird. A distinctive feature of each word is that it corresponds in a situation of communication with one concept (or denotation) regardless of the number of morphemes of which it may consist.

Another characteristic feature of the word is its ability to take different grammatical forms in speech and convey grammatical meaning.

Words in speech (and text) are linked into phrases and sentences. Many phrases have a figurative meaning, and the meaning of the constituent elements is greatly obscured, for example: a mare's nest - nonsense, to beat about the bush - to walk around and around; in other cases, individual words can only be used as part of set phrases or clichés: to shrug one's shoulders - shrug, hazel eyes - brown eyes, etc. The section of lexicology that studies phrases, stable speech turns and expressions is called phraseology.

Having considered the basic properties of the word, we can proceed to its definition. A word is a speech unit used to communicate between people, having a material embodiment in the form of a group of sounds, having a meaning and characterized by both formal and semantic unity.

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